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FEATURES OF METHODS FOR ASSESSING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TOURISM SECTOR

Abylkair Askeyev

MSc in Economics, PhD student of L.N. Gumilyov Eurasian National University

Currently, the concept and measurement of the effectiveness of tourism is attracting more and more attention in the economic literature. The reason for this lies both in the growing importance of the tourism industry, and in the growing competition in the market as a result of the transition from mass tourism to an individual approach to the specific attitudes and needs of tourists.

In this regard, the author studied Russian and foreign methods for assessing the effectiveness of tourism.

According to the results of studying Russian features of methods for assessing the effectiveness of tourism sector, the following is noted:

1. the subject of research in most scientific articles is mainly the assessment of economic efficiency;
2. the list of objects of assessment is quite diverse: from infrastructure projects to tourist destinations in the regions;
3. the degree of approbation of methods is growing;
4. the subjects of the mesolevel and groups of microunits are predominantly objects of research;
5. a synthesis of quantitative and qualitative methods;
6. a tendency to use data from international organizations;
7. existing methods are being improved.

At the same time, in the course of studying the foreign aspect of methods for assessing the effectiveness of tourism sector:

1. improving not only existing, but also developing new methods with a focus on building complex econometric models that consider the heterogeneity of international tourist destinations;
2. conducting global research at the macro level;
3. collection and active use of panel data;
4. constant interaction of scientists from different countries and universities to combine existing methods, as well as the development and testing of new ones;
5. an attempt to evaluate the effectiveness of quality indicators for the provision of services by tourist facilities, the behavioral characteristics of consumers using the analysis of big data, including the construction of neural networks, stable homology;
6. an attempt to assess the effectiveness of the use of natural and cultural heritage sites, including those included in the UNESCO World Heritage List were revealed.

In general, analyzing the works of foreign scientists it can be concluded that the costly (traditional) approach to assessing the effectiveness of the tourism sector based on measuring the ratio of economic results obtained with the costs incurred to achieve them, is the most common in studies on micro-, meso- and macro levels of the economy.

When studying the Russian aspect, it is noted mainly the application of a broad approach to the assessment of the effectiveness of tourism sector, which provides for the ratio of the obtained result (effect) with the desired one. A broad approach is convenient in the case of assessing the social aspect of efficiency, since it does not provide for the correlation of performance results with the costs of achieving them.

There are no conflicts between the use of a traditional or a broad approach in the study of the effectiveness of tourism sector.

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МОДИФИЦИРОВАННАЯ КОСТНО-ПЛАСТИЧЕСКАЯ КРАНИОТОМИЯ

Н.Ш.Месхия

Нейрохирургический центр Западной Грузии, Сухуми, и АО «Ингурский медкомплекс», Грузия

При различных клинико-анатомических формах тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы, как известно, повсеместное применение находит, в основном, одно или двухсторонняя резекционная краниотомия, которая осуществляется по средством раскусывания костей черепа и формирования трепанационных дефектов, служащих впоследствии местом развития грубых кожно-твердооболочечно-мозговых сращений. С целью их разделения и закрытия трепанационных дефектов различными гомо или гетеропластическими материалами проводятся в холодном периоде повторные вмешательства с нередким нагноительным осложнением операционной раны.

При этом один из самых анатомичных методов - метод костно-пластической краниотомии не находит, в отличие от плановых вмешательств, столь широкое применение в хирургии последствий тяжелой черепно мозговой травмы.

Применение традиционного костно-пластического метода краниотомии ограничено травматическим отеком и пролабированием мозга в трепанационный дефект – нарушением нормальных анатомических кранио-церебральных объемно-емкостных соотношений, неизбежных, в той или иной степени, при любой клинико-анатомической форме тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы.

Предлагаемый модифицированный метод костно-пластической краниотомии адаптирован к условиям отека и протрузии мозга в трепанационный дефект. Он предусматривает, как и традиционный костно-пластический метод, выпиливание костного лоскута, в отличии от резекционных методов, единым костно-надкостничным блоком.

Метод предусматривает, наряду с устранением фактора компрессии, смягчение странгуляции и интенсивности ущемления срединно-стволовых структур, вызванных первичным поражением или дислокацией мозга, что может благоприятствовать восстановлению ликворной и гемомикроциркуляции в пораженных участках и их функциональной реабилитации.

Расширенно-модифицированная костно-пластическая краниотомия осуществляется посредством наложения 5-6 фрезовых отверстий в черепе с формированием костного лоскута, диаметром не менее 15-16 см.

При угнетении сознания не ниже сопора (9-10 баллов по ШКГ), смещении срединных структур до 4 мм, пульсации мозга, функциональной сохранности орально-стволовых структур (зрачковых, корнзальных, глабеллярных рефлексов и т.д.) и при умеренном отеке мозга – при несущественном кранио-церебральном объемно-емкостном дисбалансе, расширенная костно-пластическая краниотомия производится в несколько видоизмененном, усовершенствованном виде: в конце вмешательства через 3-4 микроотверстия, наложенные вдоль края краниотомии и в симметричных местах выпиленного костного фрагмента, проводятся (в костном фрагменте дважды) лигатуры, концы которых выводятся наружу, в рану и, после пластического наращивания твердой оболочки, костно-надкостничный фрагмент наводится, как бы, в виде «фартука» на место выпиливания.

По разрешении отека мозга, костно-надкостничным фрагмент ложится на место, а при надобности, легко коррегируется провизорными лигатурами, выведенными наружу, которые завязываются не в глубине

раны, а, после проведения их сквозь кожу, вдоль операционной раны, натягиваются над валиками, уложенными вдоль краев разреза кожи, вследствие чего, костный фрагмент оказывается, как бы, в подвешенном состоянии, что исключает его компримирующий контакт с корой мозга.

Таким способом было произведено 217 оперативных вмешательств с благоприятным исходом. Лишь в 4,5% случаев отмечен летальный исход.

Преимущество модифицированного метода расширенной костно-пластической краниотомии состоит в том, что он адаптирован к условиям черепно-мозговой травмы – к условиям умеренного отека мозга и несущественного дисбаланса кранио-церебральных объемно-емкостных соотношений; в том, что он предусматривает выпиливание костного лоскута единым, цельным костно-надкостничным блоком, что исключает, в отличие от резекционной краниотомии, формирование трепанационного дефекта, служащего местом развития кожно-оболочечно-мозговых сращений; модифицированный метод костно-пластической краниотомии исключает необходимость повторных вмешательств с целью разъединения сращений и пластики трепанационных дефектов.

Модифицированный метод, как и традиционная костно-пластическая краниотомия, становится превентивным условием для послеоперационных остаточных явлений и резидуальных состояний нейротравмы; благоприятствует анатомичности репаративных процессов в ране.

**К ВОПРОСУ ДИФФЕРЕНЦИРОВАННОГО,
БИОНЕЙРОПАТОГЕНЕТИЧЕСКОГО ПОДХОДА К ВЫБОРУ
ВМЕШАТЕЛЬСТВА ПРИ РАЗЛИЧНЫХ КЛИНИКО-АНАТОМИЧЕСКИХ
ФОРМАХ ТЯЖЁЛОЙ ЧЕРЕПНО-МОЗГОВОЙ ТРАВМЫ**

Н.Ш.Месхия

проф., Нейрохирургический центр Западной Грузии, АО «Ингурский медкомплекс», Грузия

В хирургии различных клиничко-анатомических форм тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы (ЧМТ), в отличие от вмешательств на содержимом полости черепа, обозначилась тенденция отхода от ограниченных оперативных доступов к оптимально-расширенной краниотомии. Однако при этом, как и прежде, чаще других применяется, в особенности в неспециализированных стационарах, метод резекционной краниотомии, при котором не всегда учитывают патогенетические и клиничко-анатомические особенности и различия биогенеза инерционных(травм ускорения) и импрессионных,(статических) травм. Поэтому проблема дифференцированного подхода к выбору вмешательства в хирургии тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы остается актуальной.

Материал и метод: Работа основана на многолетнем опыте и анализе значительного клиничского материала, более 3500 оперативных вмешательств среди более чем 4000 пострадавших с различными клиничко-анатомическими формам ЧМТ. У 312 (7,7%) пострадавших травма была сочетанной.

В докомпьютерном периоде оперированы 1515 пострадавших, в посткомпьютерном - 1990.

С появлением адекватных средств диагностики (КТ, МРТ) появилась возможность визуальной идентификации характера и степени повреждения мозга. Это позволило осуществлять дифференцированный подход к выбору вмешательства с учетом биопатогенетических особенностей и различий клиничко-анатомических форм тяжелой ЧМТ, состояние кранио-церебральных объемно-емкостных соотношений, степени их дисбаланса, а также с учетом таких клиничко-неврологических признаков, как уровень сознания и функциональное состояние оральных стволовых структур и т.д.

При ограниченных, импрессионных (статических) повреждениях и отсутствии нарушений сознания или его угнетении до умеренного либо глубокого оглушения и сопора (до 13-14; 11-12 и 9-10 баллов соответственно по ШКГ) и негрубых стволовых функциональных нарушениях предпочтение стали отдавать традиционной или модифицированной костно-пластической краниотомии. При диффузных, инерционных (травмах ускорения) повреждениях и угнетении сознания до степени умеренной и глубокой комы (до 6-8 и 4-5 баллов по ШКГ) и дислокации срединных структур на 5 мм и более проводили широкую декомпрессивную трепанацию. При множественных гематомах и очагах ушиба мозга, в том числе в разных полушариях, проводили обширную декомпрессивную двухстороннюю трепанацию с пластическим наращиванием твердой мозговой оболочки. При повреждении лобных долей с аксиальным смещением, осуществляли бифронтальную краниотомию с фальксотомией. В компьютерном периоде во всех случаях окончательное решение – выбор характера и объема вмешательства осуществляли с учетом данных КТ или МРТ, степени смещения мозга, состояния базальных (охватывающей и межножковой) цистерн. Вмешательство, как правило, начинали как расширенную костно-пластическую трепанацию, но завершали, в зависимости от интраоперационных находок--

выраженности отека и степени пролабирования мозга в трепанационный дефект. В каждом конкретном случае выбор между костнопластической (в том числе модифицированной) краниотомией и расширенной декомпрессионной (с выпиливанием и подкожным сохранением цельного костного лоскута) трепанацией зависел от кранио-церебральных объемно-емкостных соотношений, степени их дисбаланса, уровня сознания и функционального состояния орально-стволовых структур.

Анализ материала и обсуждение. Анализ клинического материала показывает, что при субвисочной резекционной краниотомии, в связи с отсутствием достаточного обзора и возможности радикального удаления сгустков крови, в основном, полюсной и межполушарной локализации, гематомы удалялись часто лишь частично. При различных клинико-анатомических формах тяжелой ЧМТ субвисочная краниотомия, в силу своей ограниченности, устраняла лишь фактор компрессии и то часто лишь частично и вовсе не предусматривала смягчение странгуляции и ущемления мозга, вызванных дислокацией. Она, в силу неполноценности декомпрессии, не в состоянии была создавать условия для «расправления и отхода» отека мозга - для снижения интенсивности его ущемления как при боковом унко-тенториальном вклинении, так и при аксиальной дислокации и ущемлении оральных отделов ствола мозга в области тенториальной вырезки, тогда как цель любого вмешательства, как известно, должна состоять именно в этом – в смягчении интенсивности ущемления и в создании условий для функциональной реабилитации срединно-стволовых структур, чего нельзя достичь с применением таких методов вмешательства, которые априорно не обеспечивают полноценную декомпрессию содержимого полости черепа. Это возможно достичь лишь при оптимально-расширенной декомпрессии мозга. Поэтому, в случае его диффузного поражения и наличия двухсторонних и множественных гематом, а также при противоударных очагах ушиба и размозжения с дислокационным синдромом, к субвисочной резекционной краниотомии, стали прибегать все реже, а с внедрением адекватных средств диагностики (КТ и МРТ) стали придерживаться принципа широкого доступа к объемным очагам и к источнику геморрагии. Предпочтение стали отдавать расширенной краниотомии.

Резекционная краниотомия, помимо случаев оскольчато-вдавленных переломов, была изъята из практики. Тем самым, изначально исключались возможность развития грубых послеоперационных сращений в области трепанационного дефекта и необходимость производства отсеченных гомо- либо аллокраниопластики со свойственным им нередким гнойными осложнениями.

Предпочтение отдавалось широкой неплотно фиксированной костнопластической краниотомии, которую выполняли из 5-6 фрезевых отверстий с формированием костного лоскута, диаметром не менее 15-16 см. При отеке мозга и пролабировании в рану -- при обширных, в особенности эпидуральной и внутримозговых гематомах с размозжением, при снижении уровня бодрствования до 6-8 баллов по ШКГ и смещении срединных структур более 5мм, осуществляли широкую костно-пластическую трепанацию, которая завершалась декомпрессией мозга с подкожным сохранением костного фрагмента.

Среди 1990 оперативных вмешательств, выполненных в компьютерном периоде, в 902 случаях была осуществлена односторонняя декомпрессионная трепанация и в 157 – двусторонняя с цельным выпиливанием костного фрагмента и подкожным его сохранением. Умерли 454 из них (42,8%) пострадавших, которым была выполнена декомпрессионная трепанация. В остальных 894 случаях была выполнена широкая костно-пластическая краниотомия с неплотной фиксацией костного лоскута: в 84 случаях бифронтальная краниотомия с фальксотомией, у 593 пациентов –

традиционная костнопластическая трепанация и в 217 наблюдениях - модифицированная костно-пластическая краниотомия. Летальный исход был отмечен в 27 (32,1%), 110 (18,5%) и в 11 (5,1%) случаях соответственно. Сознание пострадавших с костно-пластической трепанацией было угнетено до степени оглушения и сопора. Летальность в этой группе составила 16,6%.

Послеоперационная смертность среди 1990 вмешательств с различными клинико-анатомическими формами тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы в компьютерном периоде составила 30,3 %.

Таким образом, результаты бионейропатогенетического подхода к выбору вмешательства при различных клинико-анатомических формах тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы, оказались вполне успешными: дифференцированным подходом к выбору вмешательства, с учетом биомеханизма и патоморфологических особенностей травмы, вместе с расширенной, полноценной декомпрессии мозга и постоянным компьютерно-нейрохирургическим мониторингом за динамикой процесса в послеоперационном периоде, удалось снизить, из года в год, послеоперационную смертность при различных тяжелых клинико-анатомических формах ЧМТ до 29-30%, против 36-38% докомпьютерного периода и 35-45% летальности по обобщенным данным периферийных медицинских учреждений.

Выводы: На основе многолетнего опыта и анализа значительного клинического материала - более чем 3500ый оперативным вмешательством по поводу различных клинико-анатомических форм тяжелой черепно-мозговой травмы (ЧМТ), показана эволюция взглядов на нейротравму и преимущество дифференцированного подхода к выбору вмешательства с учетом биомеханизма и нейропатоморфологических особенностей и различий клинико-анатомических форм ЧМТ; показана зависимость клинических достижений не только от устранения фактора компрессии, но и, в основном, от оптимально-расширенной, полноценной декомпрессии содержимого полости черепа – от смягчения нарушенных кранио-церебральных объемно-ёмкостных соотношений и создания условий и возможности для функциональной реабилитации срединных и орально-стволовых структур мозга.

**PATHOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE LUNGS IN COVID-19
ASSOCIATED ACUTE RESPIRATORY DISTRESS SYNDROME**

Ibadov Ravshan Alievich
Ibragimov Sardor Khamdamovich
Burkhonov Bakhodir Bakhromjonovich
Mardonov Jamshid Normurotovich

State Institution “Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center for Surgery named after academician V.Vakhidov”, State Institution “Republican Specialized Infectious Diseases Hospital Zangiota No. 1”

Objective: to study and evaluate the pathological changes of COVID-19 with severe pneumonia and its combination with ARDS syndrome using autopsy materials.

Methods. In our study, we divided the morphological changes in the lungs associated with the ARDS syndrome into 3 conventionally proposed stages, namely: the exudative stage, the fibroproliferative stage, and the fibrous stage. Thus, the mechanisms and morphological and functional signs of damage to the broncho-alveolar system were studied in three groups of patients: group 1 - patients for 1-5 days of illness, i.e. with exudative stage and early microcirculatory vasocoagulopathy; group 2 - patients on days 6-10 of illness (56 autopsies), i.e. with fibroproliferative stage (47 autopsies); group 3 - patients with more than 10 days of illness (52 autopsies), i.e. with fibrous stage.

Autopsy materials were evaluated histologically using light microscopy. At the same time, the materials obtained for light microscopy were fixed in a phosphate buffer solution of 10% formalin on Lilia, and paraffin sections were stained with hematoxylin and eosin dyes. Studies in light microscopy were carried out and photographed on an Axioscop 40 - ZEISS microscope connected to a computer via a digital camera. All images were processed and saved on a computer running Microsoft Windows 10 Pro. The results of pathoanatomical studies were obtained in their original form as the collection and study of materials continued.

Results. During the pathomorphological study of the features of COVID-19 associated ARDS using autopsy materials at different stages of the disease, a clear temporal pattern of relationships and variability of epithelial, vascular and fibrous patterns was determined, in particular:

- the histopathological picture of the first five days of the disease is characterized by exudative changes and signs of organizing pneumonia, with early microcirculatory vasocoagulopathy, a high rate of damage to the endothelium of the main capillaries and type 1 alveocytes, the formation of hyaline membranes in the alveolar tract, alveolar sac and bronchioles. The compensatory function of type 2 alveocytes is determined, exudation of the protein part of the blood with the development of pulmonary edema, the formation of fibrinous and erythrocyte-fibrinous thrombi in the cavity of the pulmonary arteries;

- the fibroproliferative stage (5-10 days of the disease) is characterized by interstitial edema with signs of fibrinous pneumonia, intraalveolar deposition of fibrin and hyaline in the alveolar membranes, microthrombosis, accumulation of pathological forms of erythrocytes, the presence of microthrombi, vascular filling, perivascular inflammation of the vascular walls;

- in the fibrous stage (more than 10 days from the onset of the disease) there are numerous hemorrhages in the visceral pleura, a change in the color of the cross section of the lungs, signs of a secondary bacterial infection, with signs of disorganization (remodeling) due to rapidly developing fibrosis. The interalveolar barrier is sharply thickened with collagen fibers, fibroblasts and myofibroblasts, the development of microangiopathy and

microvascular thrombosis of the pulmonary arteries and venous vessels of various calibers, the addition of a predominantly secondary bacterial infection, lymphocytic infiltrates are observed.

Conclusion. In the course of the study, the mechanisms and morphological and functional signs of damage to the broncho-alveolar system as the main mechanism involved in the pathogenesis of COVID-19 were studied, and the differential diagnostic characteristics of COVID-19 associated ARDS were determined. It was noted that in COVID-19 pneumonia, the underlying changes in the lungs progressed in almost the same type, while in acute respiratory distress syndrome they underwent a distinct contrast. The pathogenesis and morphological specifics of the new coronavirus, as well as the existence of different views on the morphological changes currently taking place in it, require a more comprehensive study. The preservation of controversial issues about intensive care in modern treatment tactics remains relevant.

MOLECULAR GENETIC IDENTIFICATION OF MICROORGANISMS ISOLATED FROM HOSPITALS IN ALMATY, KAZAKHSTAN

Sergey V. Shilov

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Tatyana V. Kuznetsova

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Nosocomial infections are one of the pressing medical and social problems of modern healthcare. Despite anti-epidemic measures, frequency of drug resistance occurrence, associated mortality and therapy cost continues to increase.

Thirteen strains of bacteria causing nosocomial infections were isolated from clinical material collected at the Department of Vascular Surgery of Syzganov's National Scientific Center of Surgery in Almaty, Kazakhstan. Molecular-genetic identification of the clinical isolates was carried out. The 16S rRNA gene present in all bacteria was used to detect and identify microorganisms in clinical samples. The analysis of variable regions of the 16S rRNA gene of bacteria, using specific primers for this region, was carried out by PCR using ProFlex thermal cycler (Applied Biosystems, USA). Amplification products were analyzed by electrophoresis in 2.0 % agarose gel under standard conditions. As a result, three clinical isolates were identified as belonging to the genus *Staphylococcus*, three isolates to the genus *Pseudomonas*, one isolate to the genus *Streptococcus*, three isolates to the genus *Escherichia*, and three isolates to the genus *Klebsiella*.

Identities of the clinical isolates were confirmed by analysis of partial 16S rDNA sequences used 3130 Genetic Analyzer (Applied Biosystems, USA). Sequencing of purified PCR products was carried out in the forward and reverse directions in separate reactions in four repeats, using genus-specific primers. Alignment of forward and reverse sequences for each sample was performed using the DNA Baser Assembler Version 5.15.0.0BT software package. Organisms were identified by comparing consensus sequences with known sequences stored in the NCBI database library.

**MULTILOCUS SEQUENCE TYPING OF PATHOGENS ISOLATED FROM
HOSPITALS IN ALMATY**

Tatyana V. Kuznetsova

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Sergey V. Shilov

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Nosocomial infections are a global problem of modern healthcare. The pathogens of nosocomial infections often belong to a specific clonal complex, which makes it possible to assess the risk of infection spread by the MLST type of the isolated pathogen. Multilocus sequence typing (MLST) of isolates allows identifying individual clones and clonal complexes by marker genes of pathogenic microorganisms.

We performed genotyping of 12 clinical pathogens isolated in the Department of Vascular Surgery of Syzganov's National Scientific Center of Surgery in Almaty, Kazakhstan. In research were use three strains of *Escherichia coli*, three strains of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, three strains of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, two strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, and one strain of *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Analysis of *E. coli* isolates showed belonging to three different genotypes, differing from each other by alleles of all marker genes. MLST of *K. pneumoniae* isolates showed that all three strains are close to each other in genotype and differ only in a few marker alleles. The results of the MLST of *P. aeruginosa* isolates showed that two pathogens belong to the ST308 genotype and one to the ST244 genotype. Strains of these types are widespread throughout the world and have been isolated from the lungs of patients with cystic fibrosis, as well as from blood, urine and soft tissue infectious. The database of the Danish University of Technology in Copenhagen was used for MLST of gram-positive bacteria belonging to the species *S. aureus* and *Str. pneumoniae*. *S. aureus* isolates included two genotypes – ST508 and ST30. These two pathogens differed from each other in five of the seven marker alleles. *Str. pneumoniae* was belonging to the genotype ST377. It is characterized by resistance to chloramphenicol, penicillin and cefotaxime, but is sensitive to tetracycline and erythromycin.

**IN VITRO EVALUATION OF THE IODINE-BASED COORDINATION
COMPOUNDS CYTOTOXICITY**

Natalya V. Zubenko

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Raikhan A. Parenova

MSc in Biotechnology, scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Ludmila N. Ivanova

Epidemiologist, Deputy Head of the Virology Laboratory, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Increasing levels of resistance and decreasing newly discovered drugs have led to a global health crisis. The widespread use of antibiotics, their wide availability, additional prescription for viral infections, the wrong choice of the drug, its dosage regimen or duration of treatment, and non-compliance by patients with medical recommendations lead to the formation and spread of antibiotic-resistant strains of microorganisms. Drug-resistant diseases already cause at least 700,000 deaths globally a year, a figure that could increase to 10 million deaths globally per year by 2050 under the most alarming scenario if no action is taken.

To prevent the spread of antibiotic resistance, public health needs to invest in research and development of new antibiotics, vaccines, diagnostics and other tools.

Of particular importance are iodine-containing drugs, which have a number of advantages. The development of methods for obtaining new types of drugs based on iodine is an important and urgent problem today. All pathogens of microbial infections are sensitive to iodine, and the formation of acquired resistance to iodine-containing drugs has never been recorded.

JSC "SCAID" carries out the search, development and synthesis of domestic antimicrobial agents with their initial biological screening, preclinical and clinical trials.

In view of the fact that the drug candidate safety is of paramount importance when studying the properties of the developed drugs, we conducted a study of the cytotoxicity effect of nine iodine containing drugs. To study cytotoxicity, we used cell lines that differ in organ affiliation and, at the same time, are alternative analogues of cells of a living organism: MDCK, RD, BHK-21 and HepG2. The cytotoxic effect of the studied drugs was carried out using the MTT test. Data were recorded after 72 h of drug exposure. Based on the obtained data, the CC_{50} values were calculated.

The obtained data will be used in *in silico* modeling of the relationship of biological activity on the structure of compounds.

DETERMINATION OF THE LEVEL OF THYROID HORMONES IN RATS AFTER TREATMENT BY COORDINATION COMPOUND OF IODINE OF A CHRONIC INFECTIOUS AND INFLAMMATORY DISEASE

Ludmila N. Ivanova

Epidemiologist, Deputy Head of the Virology Laboratory, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Natalya V. Zubenko

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Raikhana A. Parenova

MSc in Biotechnology, scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

An assessment of the induction of the level of thyroid hormones in the treatment of chronic infectious and inflammatory disease during therapy with an iodine coordination compound was carried out. The level of thyroid hormones in animals (rats) was determined by enzyme immunoassay. To determine the level of thyroid hormones, blood serum of experimental and control rats of both sexes was used. Animals received orally the medicinal substance IF at a dose of 62.5 mg/kg. The control group of animals received water in an amount of 0.5 ml.

Determination of the level of thyroid hormones T3-total, T3-free, T4-total, T4-free showed that the values of all test groups of animals did not differ from the control groups and corresponded to the physiological norm. In animals that treatment by the medicinal substance IF at a dose of 62.5 mg/kg for 28 days, a reduced TSH level was determined with normal free T4. Low TSH levels in old animals make it possible to suspect the onset of hyperthyroidism. These data indicate the development of mild subclinical thyrotoxicosis in old animals

Thus, the level of thyroid hormones in experimental animals, after 28 days treated by medicinal substance IF at a dose of 62.5 mg/kg, showed its high biological activity against the thyroid gland in old animals. Indicators of the biological activity of a substance is its effect on the level of TSH.

In the remaining groups, the drug does not affect the functional activity of the thyroid gland: the levels of all hormones are within the physiological norm.

**EXPLORING THE INFLUENCE OF IODINE-CONTAINING COMPOUNDS ON
THE QUORUM SENSING**

Raikhan A. Parenova

MSc in Biotechnology, scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Ludmila N. Ivanova

Epidemiologist, Deputy Head of the Virology Laboratory, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Sergey V. Shilov

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Tatyana V. Kuznetsova

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Natalya V. Zubenko

MSc in Biology, senior scientist, Virology Laboratory, Scientific Center for Anti-Infectious Drugs, Almaty, Kazakhstan

Currently, there is a transition from the traditional idea of bacteria as strictly unicellular organisms to the idea of microbial communities as integral structures that regulate their behavioral reactions depending on changes in living conditions. Also, recent studies have shown that the Quorum Sensing system performs global regulation of a large number of cellular processes in bacteria of various taxonomic groups. However, studies of the mechanisms of this system have been conducted only for a limited number of bacterial strains.

To study the variability of the animal microbiome in the treatment of iodine-containing drugs of chronic infectious and inflammatory disease, the sequencing of total RNA. RNA samples were collected after the flushing of the intestines of animals was carried out. Total bacterial RNA was initially purified from transport RNA. Sampled RNA was converted to cDNA and sequenced. The sequencing was performed using the on Torrent PGM according to the manufacturer's protocols. Generated DNA reads were quality trimmed and filtered using the raw DNA read processing pipeline implemented in Unipro UGENE v1.32.0 using 20 as the quality threshold. Reads shorter than 30 bp were filtered out. The differential gene expression was estimated using the Bioconductor-DESeq2 software package. Gene expression was determined by the alignment of the obtained reads according to the previously obtained and deposited in the NCBI relevant reference genome of the *S. aureus* model culture (CP033505).

It was found that the iodine coordination compound has an indifferent effect on the model bacterial culture. There was no significant difference in the degree of expression of genes belonging to the quorum-sensing system between the study groups.

Humanities, Literature & Arts

- *African Studies & History*
- *American Literature & Studies*
- *Asian Studies & History*
- *Canadian Studies & History*
- *Chinese Studies & History*
- *Communication*
- *Drama & Theater Arts*
- *English Language & Literature*
- *Epistemology & Scientific History*
- *Ethnic & Cultural Studies*
- *Feminism & Women's Studies*
- *Film*
- *Foreign Language Learning*
- *French Studies*
- *Gender Studies*
- *History*
- *Humanities, Literature & Arts (general)*
- *Language & Linguistics*
- *Latin American Studies*
- *Literature & Writing*
- *Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies*
- *Music & Musicology*
- *Philosophy*
- *Religion*
- *Sex & Sexuality*
- *Visual Arts*

**WAYS OF DEVELOPING TASKS ON LANGUAGE SKILLS (IN THE
FRAMEWORK OF UPDATED EDUCATION)**

Meiramkul Bakiraevna Absatova

Master of Science in Pedagogy, expert at the «Center of Pedagogical Measurements» of AEO «Nazarbayev Intellectual Schools»

One of the conditions for the best implementation of the criterion-based assessment system in the country is the provision of teachers with the methodological recommendations on assessment procedures, qualitative assessment tools, electronic document management and with accountability systems. The problem of developing assessment tools (assessment criteria, levels of thinking skills, tasks, descriptors, mark schemes) takes an important place in teachers' daily practices. Efficiency and effectiveness of assessment practices directly depend on the quality of the developed tasks. Developed assessment criteria and tasks help to reveal not only the knowledge level but also the level of higher order thinking skills (how students speak, discuss, identify the main problem and draw conclusions, listen to others, make decisions independently, and apply the acquired knowledge in their everyday lives). Language teachers' ability to develop and use high-quality assessment tools directly affects the effectiveness of their teaching experience and their work with students, especially in supporting and responding to the needs of students with low academic performance.

Writing tasks that require an extended answer allow students to define various aspects of the topic and develop logically coherent arguments.

In listening tasks, students understand different types of conversations and the mass media language, they also choose the information and summarize it. In the tasks aiming at expressing thoughts and viewpoints, students do not share their own opinions but find the answer in the context.

In reading tasks, the student works with the text, demonstrates reading skills (reading to identify the main idea, identify specific information and conclusions), and summarizes, conveys their thoughts carefully, logically, and in effective ways.

Speaking tasks are initially given in an easy form around the personal topics and further complicated to develop a discussion with a logical sequence. Tasks should expand the topic and increase the student's interest. In this way, students will get used to expressing their thoughts but not just making arguments.

Tasks related to language skills, practical examples, and development requirements help teachers organize and conduct assessments. Assessment criteria and tasks determine not only the level of knowledge but also reveal students' ability to apply the acquired knowledge and higher order thinking skills. High-quality assessment tools allow teachers to obtain objective information about the level of acquired curriculum by their students, identify the difficulties and make changes to the educational process in a timely manner.

Social Sciences

- *Academic & Psychological Testing*
- *African Studies & History*
- *Anthropology*
- *Archaeology*
- *Architecture*
- *Asian Studies & History*
- *Bioethics*
- *Canadian Studies & History*
- *Chinese Studies & History*
- *Cognitive Science*
- *Criminology, Criminal Law & Policing*
- *Development Economics*
- *Diplomacy & International Relations*
- *Early Childhood Education*
- *Economic History*
- *Education*
- *Educational Administration*
- *Educational Psychology & Counseling*
- *Educational Technology*
- *Environmental & Occupational Medicine*
- *Environmental Law & Policy*
- *Epistemology & Scientific History*
- *Ethics*
- *European Law*
- *Family Studies*
- *Feminism & Women's Studies*
- *Forensic Science*
- *Geography & Cartography*
- *Health Policy & Medical Law*
- *Higher Education*
- *History*
- *Human Migration*
- *Human Resources & Organizations*
- *International Law*
- *Law*
- *Library & Information Science*
- *Middle Eastern & Islamic Studies*
- *Military Studies*
- *Paleontology*
- *Political Science*
- *Public Health*
- *Public Policy & Administration*
- *Science & Engineering Education*
- *Sex & Sexuality*
- *Social Sciences (general)*
- *Social Work*
- *Sociology*
- *Special Education*
- *Sustainable Development*
- *Teaching & Teacher Education*
- *Technology Law*
- *Urban Studies & Planning*

**SOLUTION OF THE PROBLEM OF THE LEGAL STATUS OF THE “ASTANA”
INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL CENTER IN KAZAKHSTAN**

Farkhad Karagussov

doctor of Law, professor at Caspian University (Almaty, Kazakhstan), associate member of the International Academy of Comparative Law (IACL)

In accordance with the Constitutional Law dated 7 December 2015 the “Astana” International Financial Center (AIFC) was established in Kazakhstan as a formation that has its own bodies, enjoys the right to prescribe specific behavior within its allocated territory, create its own legal norms, introduce and implement its own administrative procedures, as well as, by the activities of the AIFC Court, to resolve disputes and conflicts. and to make decisions on the merits. On the territory of the AIFC, Kazakh law practically does not apply. Jurisdiction of bodies and courts of Kazakhstan does not extend to the territory of the AIFC. The AIFC Court may, at its discretion, resolve disputes and conflicts taking into account any considerations that are not legal norms of either Kazakh law or law of any other recognized legal system.

Some Kazakh scholars expressed an opinion that, with the creation of the AIFC, Kazakhstan can be considered a hybrid or mixed jurisdiction. It seems, that such view lacks appropriate fundamental and scientific grounds. Under current circumstances the AIFC has not been (and should not be!) recognized as a separate or otherwise distinct jurisdiction by any State. Kazakhstan has also failed to appropriately recognize it as such. However, by creation of the AIFC, our State allowed the loss of its control over application of Kazakh law in resolving disputes and conflicts that arose on the territory of our Republic within the framework of our legal system, but by will of parties to particular disputes (conflicts) were transferred to the AIFC Court for final resolution. To the maximum extent possible, the AIFC can be considered as an exorbitant jurisdiction. Accordingly, all decisions rendered by the AIFC Court cannot (or should not) be recognized by foreign courts. In general, there is a high probability of various risks that are created by the functioning of the AIFC for Kazakhstan and for all participants of private-law relations. The AIFC’s activity leads to incidents that cannot be regulated and resolved in accordance with norms of Kazakhstani legislation. The AIFC’s legal status does not allow to properly apply mechanisms and tools existing in private international law for resolving conflicts of legal systems within particular legal relations involving a foreign element.

Adoption of a political and legal decision on liquidation of the AIFC, an assessment of the consequences of its functioning and, if negative consequences are revealed, development and implementation of an action plan to eliminate them now seems to be urgent.

ӘДЕБИЕТТІК ОҚУ ПӘНІ АРҚЫЛЫ БАСТАУЫШ СЫНЫП ОҚУШЫЛАРЫН АДАМГЕРШІЛІККЕ ТӘРБИЕЛЕУ

Кожгельдиева Сауле Скендиловна

Педагогика ғылымдарының кандидаты, доцент, Қ.А.Ясауи атындағы Халықаралық қазақ-түрік университеті (Қазақстан)

Өткен ғасырдың 90-шы жылдардың басында алдыңғы қатарлы ғалым-педагогтар Мәскеуде өткен пікір-таласта мектептердегі тәрбие жұмысына сындық тұрғыдан былайша баға берген еді: Қазіргі кезде мектептердегі тәрбие жұмысының сапасы төмендеді. Императивтік келістен қол үзген педагогикалық ұжымдар оқу–процесін ізгілендіру мен демократияландырудың оңтайлы әдістері мен жолдарын жасай алмады. Қазіргі мектеп, мұғалімдер қауымы оқыту мен тәрбиелеудің, қарама-қайшылықты женудің, өтпелі кезеңнің ерекшеліктерін ескеретін әр түрлі вариантты тәрбиелік жүйелерді құрудың ғылыми негізделген технологиясын жасауды қажет етеді. Халық шаруашылық өмірін жандандыруда өзін ақтаған қоғамда болып жатқан өзгерістерде іскерлік, кәсіпкерлік, іске берілгендік сияқты оң нәтижелермен қатар, жастардың қоғамдық белсенділігінде, қоршаған ортаны қорғауында, мейірімділігінде және т.б. теріс тұстар да байқалуда. Оған мыналар да жатады: тұтынушылық пейіл, материалдық жағдайын кез келген құралмен жақсартуға ұмтылу, жеке меншікке қол сұғу, нашақорлықтың таралуы және т.б.

Жастардың жағдайын күрделендіріп отырған факторлардың біріне қоғамда жастар арасында адамгершіліктің құлдырауы, жастардың бір бөлігінің рухсыздығы, кәмелетке толмағандардың қылмысы мен тәртіп бұзуының өсуі, халықтың, оның ішінде балалардың адамгершілік ахуалының нашарлауы жатады.

Тәрбиелік стратегия ізгіліктілік, азаматтық, еңбексүйгіштік, елжандылық сияқты жалпыадамзаттық құндылықтарға негізделіп құрылуы тиіс. Олардың қатарында ұжымшылдық проблемасы өткір қойылып отыр. Өкінішке орай көптеген жылдар бойы бұл термин жеке мүддені қоғам мүддесіне бағындыру деп біржақты түсіндіріліп келді. Шындығында ұжымшылдық жеке жауапкершілікке немесе бәсекелестікке қарсы қойыла алмайды. Ұжымшыл адамды тәрбиелеу психологиясы адам-орындаушыны, конформисті тәрбиелеудің баламасы болып табылады.

Жалпы адамгершілік принциптер “өлтірме”, “алдама”, “ұрлама”.

Моральдық реттеуде сондай-ақ ұят, жеке бастың ар-намысын сезіну, абырой сияқты категориялар маңызды орын алады. Моральдың негізгі категориялары мыналар болып табылады: қайырымдылық пен зұлымдық, парыз бен ұят, абырой мен адамдық ар-намыс.

Адамдардың моральдық бейнесін анықтайтын іргелі адамдық сапаларға мыналар жатады: қиналу, мейірімділік, қайырымды іс жасау тілегі, зұлымдыққа қарсы тұру, байсалдылық, адамдық, шыдамдылық. Бірақ осы және осы сияқты басқа сапаларды біреулердің шектен тыс байып, ал екіншілердің шегіне жете кедейленген экономикалық және саяси теңсіздігі жағдайында қоғам өміріне енгізу қиын.

Қазіргі қоғамдағы моральдық – саяси жағдай бұқаралық коммуникация құралдары ақшаға табынуды қатыгездікті, ана тіліне немқұрайдылықты, азғындықты насихаттап отырғандықтан күрделене түсуде. *қайырымдылық, ұят және мейірімділік* қазір құнсызданды, ал жағдайды тез жақсарту, байлық жоғары құндылық шеніне көтерілді, оған кез келген тәсілмен, кез келген жолмен жету мақсатқа айналды, байлыққа бас ұрады, оны мақтан санайды”.

Адамгершілікке тәрбиелеу процесінде мынадай көптеген адамгершілік категориялардың, ұғымдардың мағынасы ашылады: *қайырымдылық пен зұлымдық, теңдік, әділеттік, абырой, ұят, парыз, ар-намыс* және т.б. Оқушыларға мынаны хабарлау керек: жалпыадамзаттың *адамгершілік принциптер мен нормалар* барлық халықтар мен нәсілдер үшін ортақ адамгершілік принциптер мен нормалар арқылы анықталды. Тәрбие үшін мынау маңызды: мораль адамдардың *бірігу, ынтымақтасу* және барлығы үшін *бірдей міндетті заңдар* бойынша өмір сүру қажеттігін білдіреді.

Адамгершілік сабақтарын оқу пәндерінің жүйесіне енгізу – күрделі процесс. Бірақ бастауыш мектептің адамгершілік сабақтарын, этика, эстетика, мінез-құлық мәдениеті және т.б. бойынша адамгершілік сабақтарын өткізу тәжірибесі бар. Сондықтан мұндағы мәселе бастауыш мектептің адамгершілік білім беруді жүзеге асыру мұқтажына адекватты жауап беретін мазмұн мен тиімді әдістерді табуда.

Адамгершілік сабақтарының мақсаты – балаларда олардың мінез-құлқы мен құлықтары жөніндегі түсініктерін қалыптастыру, кейін басқа адамдарды және өмірлік жағдайларды түсінуде бағдарларға айналатын белгілі бір адамгершілік ұғымдарды түсіндіру.

Көркем әдебиет пен өнер баланың сезімі мен ақылына, оның мінез-құлқына қолайлы әсерін тигізеді. Балалармен бірлесіп талқылайтын туындыларды және кейіпкерлердің, оқиғалардың адамгершілік мәні бейнеленген мәселелерді іріктеп алу - мұғалім жұмысындағы маңызды міндеттердің бірі. Әдеби кейіпкерлердің мінез-құлық мотивтерін ашатын мәтіндерді балаларға талдап беру мұғалімге материалды қорытындылауға, балалардың өз қылықтарын кейіпкердің қылығымен салыстыруға мүмкіндік береді: “Кейбір туындылар “жақсы” жөнінде, “жаман” жөнінде айқын түсінік береді. Бірақ көбінесе авторлар не “жақсының” және не “жаманның” бір мәнді еместігіне ойлануға мәжбүр етеді. Мұғалімнің жетекшілігімен олар адамдардың арасындағы күрделі өзара қарым-қатынас жөнінде, олардың сан алуан мінездері жөнінде, әр түрлі адамдардың әр себептер бойынша рухани толқуларының ерекшеліктері жөнінде ойлануы тиіс.

Көптеген жылдар бойы педагогтар мен әдіскерлер мына мәселелерді шешті және шешуде: кіші жастағы баланы әдебиет әлеміне қалай енгізу керек? Оқуды қалай үйрету керек? Кітапты сүюді қалай үйрету керек? Тарих көптеген ізденістер мен бағыттарды біледі. Бұларға мыналар жатады: “түсіндірмелік оқу”, “әдеби – көркемдік оқу”, “тәрбиелік оқу”, “сыныптық оқу” және “сыныптан тыс оқу”. Бұл – оқушыларды әдебиет әлеміне апаратын жол іздеудегі қиындықтар.

Қайырымдылықты, адалдықты, шыншылдықты, өз сөзінде тұру іскерлігін балалар жоғары бағалайды. Олар достық сезімдердің, қатынастардың байқалуын осыдан көреді. Бұл мәселелер бойынша әңгімелесу балаларға қызық. Олар өмірдің осы жағын тануға, сәйкес білім алуға мұқтаж. Әңгімелесу адамгершілік ұғымдарды анықтауға, балалардың тәжірибесін қорытындылауға және бағалауға ықпал етеді, оларды әрекетке, әлдеқайда күрделі жағдайларда ескере отырып жаңа жағдайларда мінез-құлық таңдап алуға ықпал етеді.

Қазіргі кездегі бастауыш оқыту оқушылардың қабілеттерін дамытатындай болып құрылған: оқу материалын белсенді игеру дағдыларын қалыптастырады, алған білімдерін қоршаған дүниені тануға бағытталған білімдердің тұтас жүйесіне қосуға жеткізеді. Ойлаудың дамуы, оқу материалымен жасалатын жұмыстың әр түрлі тәсілдерін игеру балалардың адамгершілік білімдерді игеруіне тікелей ықпал етеді; оқу процесін ұйымдастыру және оның әдістері адамгершілік тәжірибені жинақтауға ықпал жасайды.

E-LEARNING APPROACHES: STUDENTS' PERSPECTIVES

Nathan Minuk

High School Student, Matrix Academy High School Toronto, Ontario, Canada

In the wave of COVID-19 pandemic e-learning became one of the most desirable educational platforms. Currently, online high schools in Ontario, Canada use two approaches to virtual classes: synchronous and asynchronous. Under the first approach, classes are taught in a face-to-face virtual format where students can easily communicate with their teachers and peers. By contrast, asynchronous method of education requires students to learn on their own while completing assignments and taking tests and final exams. A pilot study has been designed to evaluate both approaches while assessing students' academic achievements and general attitude. Brief results are presented below.

The study involved ten 15–16-year-old students who attended both synchronous and asynchronous high school courses. There were students from Canada, Ukraine, Georgia, and Kazakhstan. All the participants were required to attend at least one course through the synchronous platform and one course through asynchronous learning. Students were presented with a questionnaire that involved 10 questions aimed to assess students' academic achievements and general aptitude through both modes of learning. Specifically, participants were asked how they performed on each type of course and what type of challenges they encountered during their studies. The results showed that seven of the students performed significantly better on synchronous courses. Furthermore, two participants did not finish asynchronous courses and even asked to be transferred to real life course format. Nine of ten students reported that they did not enjoy the asynchronous mode because they could not communicate with their teachers and peers, and they found a social factor to be crucial for their academic performance. Meanwhile, one of the students showed preference toward asynchronous approach that allows more flexibility in terms of time.

Given that this is a pilot study it is too early to make conclusions about two learning approaches. However, it is plausible to suggest that a social factor is essential for students' academic achievements, and it needs to be considered for teaching strategies. The results of the study might be interesting for educators who are planning to design virtual courses. The author hopes that the study will be extended in the future by involving more participants and examining various factors.

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